

Irradiation of Tissue Equivalent Substitute: Simulation and Experiment

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Abstract-: Soft and lung tissue equivalent substitute (STES and LTES) with achieved densities of 1.04 g m^{-3} and 0.25 g m^{-3} respectively were produced in this study from urethane rubber material. These densities agreed with the publication 74 of International Commission on Radiological Protection. The elemental compositions of the tissue substitutes were obtained from XCOM software analysis. For STES: H (4.53%), C (49.56%), N (5.36%), O (27.21%) and Ca (13.34%) and for the LTES: H (4.82%), C (53.44%), N (4.87%), O (24.73) and Ca (12.14%). The idealized photon irradiation simulation of the substitutes was achieved using MCNPX radiation code (version 2.7e), the elemental composition represents the material input. The substitutes were subjected to physical x-ray exposure in a diagnostic facility within machine potential range of 70kVp to 122kVp at interval of 15% increase in the kVp and 50% decrease in the mAs in accordance to the 15% rule applicable in x-radiography. The absorb dose by the substitutes from the exposure were measured with the aid of optically stimulated luminescence nanodots. The fluence (p/cm^2) and the kerma (MeV/g) results obtained directly from simulation (with relative error < 0.05) were used to estimate the simulation absorb dose and the corresponding conversion coefficients. The absorb dose from simulation and x-radiography experiment compare favorably. The coefficients obtained from simulation also compared favorably with published data. The dose to fluence and the kerma to fluence obtained in this study agree with ICRP publication 116 and 119 respectively. The photon flux to dose agreed in the diagnostic energy range but higher in the radiotherapy energy range when compared with the ANSI/ANS 1977 data. Hence, the STES and LTES developed in this study are suitable for radiation planning and as research surrogates to mimic the soft and lung tissues when irradiated.

Keywords: Simulation, Tissue Equivalent Substitute; Photon Irradiation; MCNPX; Soft Tissue; Lung Tissue

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Introduction

The use of tissue equivalent substitutes is a recommended way to create an approximate surrogate of the human body[1]. And the use of conversion coefficient is an acceptable practice in the estimation of the absorbed radiation dose by the human body, including the internal organs. Estimating the conversion coefficient are achieved by measuring the Kerma or the fluence[2] of the incident photon energy. Conversion coefficients are mostly the ratio of two radiation protection or operation quantities. Radiation protection quantities are ICRP specified dosimetric quantities, specified in the human body while the operational quantities are the quantities in which it's measurement showcase its agreement with the radiation protection systems[1]. This study intends to report the dose conversion coefficient of urethane-based tissue substitute. These tissue substitutes have shown similar properties to the soft and lung tissue[3]. It has been confirmed that conversion coefficients are dependents on physical parameters and properties like the mass density, mass energy absorption coefficients, mass attenuation coefficients and so on. It is therefore reasonable to assume that there can never be a singular dataset that can satisfy every material, considering diverse conditional possibilities and different energy bins involved in irradiation procedures.

This gap led to different opinion on conversion coefficients in the field of radiation science[4]. It is the opinion of this study that every tissue substitute or material have a peculiar conversion coefficient.

Equivalent Tissue Substitute

Tissue equivalent substitutes are artificial materials with properties like the human tissue. They are used to mimic human tissues and they are relevant in construction of radiation phantoms[5]–[7]. They are useful for diagnoses, routine control, therapeutic, quality assurance and for research purposes. They are also used to measure doses received by patients during medical examinations[3], [8], [9]. The idea of bioprinting could be a another great leap in using tissue substitute for organ reconstruction[10]–[12].

Dose Conversion Coefficient, DCC

Dose Conversion Coefficient, DCC is the ratio of the absorb dose, D to the Kerma, K in air. The absorb dose is the mean energy received by the absorbing medium in a unit volume per unit mass in the same volume while Kerma, K is the kinetic energy transferred or liberated from the charged particles in a volume per the mass in the same volume[13]. In the assessment of radiation dosimetry, DCC

is an important physical quantity[2][14]; and it is mostly derived from Monte Carlo simulation on computational human phantoms[15]–[20]. The immediate assessment of acute radiation dose due to the emergency after accidental radiation exposure is key but it can be difficult, and inaccurate due to uncertainties in the readings but the availability of DCC can make such estimates easy and reliable[21]. This assessment is also applicable to the workers and adult public members that are exposed to environmental radiations from nuclear plant in accidental or normal situations[22]. The values of DCC is dependent on the phantom geometry[23] and physique[24], hence, it is paramount to define the geometry of the phantom and the physique when reporting the dose conversion coefficients.

Fluence to Dose, D_T/ϕ

This is obtained as the ratio of the tissue absorb dose, D_T to the fluence, ϕ . The fluence is the quotient dN by da where dN is the number of particles received by a spherical material of cross-sectional area, da [13]. In MCNPX results, fluence is readily available using F4 tally but the absorb dose must be estimated. The D_T/ϕ is a very useful tool in radiation assessment[7-9][27] and it has also been adopted in radiological assessment of atomic bomb survivors[28]. It is also dependent on the phantom geometry and the physique[29].

Fluence to Kerma, K/ϕ

The fluence to Kerma conversion coefficient, K/ϕ is similar to the D_T/ϕ with the unit, pGycm^2 . The quotient of D_T/ϕ by K/ϕ yield the dose conversion coefficient, D_T/K . The K/ϕ is a very useful tool in dose assessment [30]

A. Photon-Flux to Dose, $DF(E)$

The photon-flux to dose conversion coefficient defines the quotient, equivalent dose rate by the fluence rate. The unit is $(\text{rem/hr})/(\text{p/cm}^2.\text{s})$. The $DF(E)$ dataset are available in different publications: ANS/ANSI 1977, ANS/ANSI 1991 (ANS 1991 was withdrawn in 2001), ICRP 21 and ICRP 74 but the most commonly used is the ANSI 1977 version[31]. The use of dose function code in MCNP[32] enhances the dose modification of the output result in MCNPX and it makes the estimation of $DF(E)$ easy.

Experimental Method

Tissue Substitute, NIST XCOM and MCNPX

The lung and the soft tissues were modelled using the mixture of urethane product PMC 120/30 Dry, calcium carbonate and polystyrene according to reference [33]. The soft tissue equivalent substitute was produced by mixing the PMC part A, part B and the calcium carbonate in the ratio

1:1:1. The lung tissue equivalent substitute was produced by mixing the soft tissue and the polystyrene beads in the ratio 10:1. The air bubbles in the materials were extracted before they are allowed to set for 48hours. The densities were obtained from five samples and the variation is approximately ± 0.01 , this is to ascertain uniform mass distribution in the materials. Tissue equivalent substitutes of different types, depending on their material properties have useful applications at various levels of radiation research. The NIST XCOM software was used to achieve the elemental composition of the two substitutes. These were used in the MCNPX radiation exposure. The dose cards were used for the photon flux to dose coefficients. High particle number and high computation time were used to keep the relative error below 0.05. The simulation was achieved using the MCNPX Visual Plotter version 2.7E installed on a PC with Intel(R) Core (TM) i3-6100U, 2.3GHz processor, 64-bit OS and 4.00 GB RAM. The specification of the radiation source is Ir-192; density, $\rho = 22.56\text{g/cm}^3$. The other library details include ZAID: 77193.30y, AWR: 192.96300, MCNP Library: LLLDOS, LLNL/ACTL Date: <1983 Length: 243. Forty-three energy bins were used between 0.06MeV-15.0MeV and twenty-eight energy bins for the dose modified simulation between 0.1MeV-15.0MeV were investigated

Equations

The F4 tally [32] is defined as:

$$F4 = \frac{1}{V} \int_V dV \int_E dE \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \Phi(r, E, \Omega) \quad (1)$$

The modified F4 tally output [32] is defined by:

$$F4 = \frac{1}{V} \int_V dV \int_E dE \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \mathfrak{R}(E) \Phi(r, E, \Omega) \quad (2)$$

Where $\mathfrak{R}(E)$ is the fluence to dose conversion factor. The relative error in the $DF(E)$ is obtained from[34]

$$RE_{DF(E)} = \sqrt{(\phi_{RE})^2 + (K_{RE})^2} \quad (3)$$

Results and Discussion

Dose to Kerma, D_T/K

The trend of D_T/K with respect to the photon energy is similar for the lung, Figure 1 and the soft tissue, Figure 2 agree with the result from [35]. The value of D_T/K increases between 0.06-0.076MeV, then decreases to the minimum at 0.078MeV. It increases again until it attains a second peak value at 1.25MeV which coincide with the energy bin at which the positron annihilation is first observed.

Figure 1: D_T/K vs Energy: LTES

Figure 2: D_T/K vs Energy: STES

Kerma to Fluence, K/ϕ and Dose to Fluence, D_T/ϕ

The D_T/ϕ obtained in this study is compared with the ICRP 116 values while the K/ϕ is compared with the ICRP 119 values. In both cases, it is observed that the ICRP values are far greater than the values of this study, but the trend is similar. The observed trend for this study confirmed a lower dose compared to the ICRP values, which by implication point to a safer radiation dose parameter. The trend is similar for the lung tissue, Figure 3 and the soft tissue, Figure 4.

Figure 3: K/ϕ and D_T/ϕ (pGy/cm^2) vs Energy: LTES

Figure 4: K/ϕ and D_T/ϕ (pGy/cm^2) vs Energy: STES

Photon Flux to Dose Ratio $DF(E)$

The $DF(E)$ obtained for the lung tissue, Figure 5 and the soft tissue, Figure 7 exhibit the same trend when compared with the values of ANSI/ANS 1977. Although, the curve obtained for this study ‘ride’ above the ANS values but the similarity in their trend show a possibility of convergence at higher energies. A very similar trend is observed as the curve of $DF(E)$ for ICRP 74 ‘ride’ above the $DF(E)$ of ICRP 116 in a related manner[4]. It was computationally confirmed that the $DF(E)$ of lung and soft tissue material converged with the ANS values at 15.0MeV[31].

The relative error in the $DF(E)$ for the lung tissue, Figure 6 has a peak value of 0.055 at the first energy bin (0.07MeV) but the relative error thereafter declines rapidly to 0.003 at 15.0MeV. The relative error for the soft tissue, Figure 8 exhibit similar trend. It has a peak value of 0.067 at the first energy bin (0.007MeV) but it decreases to 0.003 at 15.0MeV. The low relative errors attest to the reliability of the result.

Figure 5: Graph of $DF(E)$ vs Energy: LTES

Figure 6: Graph of Relative Error, RE vs Energy: LTES

Figure 7: Graph of DF(E) vs Energy - STES

Figure 8: Graph of Relative Error, RE vs Energy - STES

The Absorb Dose: Experiment and Simulation

The dose received by the soft and the lung tissue from radiations during x-radiography experiment were presented in Figure 9 and the absorb dose from simulation are presented in Figure 10. From the figures, the trend of the absorb dose from simulation and experiment compare favorably. The sharp turning point in the simulation absorb dose is however observed but the trend compares favorably.

Figure 9: Total Dose Received from X-Ray Exposure (STES and LTES)

Figure 10: Total Dose Received from Simulation of Idealized Photon Exposure (STES and LTES)

Conclusion

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The coefficients estimated in this study present a reduced radiation dose compared to the ICRP values, indicating safe radiation absorb dose when used as a tissue substitute during radiotherapy planning or research.

Author Contribution

The authors contributed equally

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest to declare

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